

THE FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF STITCHED GRP LAMINATES FOLLOWING UNDERWATER EXPLOSION SHOCK LOADING

A.P. Mouritz

Defence Science and Technology Organisation, Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory,
P.O. Box 4331, Melbourne, Australia 3000.

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the flexural behaviour of glass reinforced polymer (GRP) laminates stitched with Kevlar® following underwater explosion shock loading. Prior to underwater shock loading, the flexural strength of the stitched GRP laminates was about 10% lower than non-stitched GRP, and this reduction was caused by microstructural damage resulting from the stitching process. When the non-stitched and stitched laminates were impulsively loaded by a low pressure shock wave, they experienced little damage and consequently their flexural properties were only slightly lower compared with the materials before shock testing. When loaded by a high pressure shock wave, some of the laminates suffered extensive damage in the form of cracking of the polymer and glass fibres together with delaminations. In general, the amount of damage was lower in the stitched laminates compared with the non-stitched laminates, although it depended on the stitch orientation and stitch density. Consequently, the residual flexural properties of the stitched laminates were higher than the non-stitched laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced polymer (GRP) laminates are being used increasingly in the construction of small naval vessels, such as fast patrol boats and mine countermeasures ships, and in the fins and fairings of submarines [1]. GRP is lighter and more corrosion resistance than traditional naval materials, such as steel and aluminium, and has good stealth properties (low electrical and magnetic signatures), which makes the vessel more difficult to detect by radar. A major threat to naval vessels during war-time operations is the close-in explosion of a submerged munition, such as a sea-mine or torpedo. The shock wave generated by an underwater explosion exerts a high-pressure impulse load on the vessels' hull, possibly resulting in severe structural damage to the laminate. Damage to GRP usually involves cracking of the polymer matrix, buckling and fracture of the glass fibres, and delaminations, producing significant reductions in the fatigue resistance and tensile, compressive and flexural strengths [2-5]. There is considerable interest in improving the damage resistance and post-shock mechanical properties of GRP laminates for naval vessels, and recent studies have shown that the spread of delamination damage arising from point-impact loading may be reduced by reinforcing laminates through-the-thickness by stitching with carbon, glass or Kevlar® fibres [6]. Mouritz [7] studied the response of stitched GRP laminates under

explosive loading, and found that the spread of delamination damage was reduced compared with the non-stitched laminate, however high amounts of damage were localised around the stitches. After shock loading, the residual tensile strengths of the non-stitched and stitched laminates were similar. This paper extends this study to examine the effect of underwater explosive shock loading on the flexural properties of GRP laminates stitched with Kevlar®.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The GRP laminates were made from E-glass fibres and a vinyl ester polymer. The laminates contained two types of glass ply: woven roving and chopped strand mat, and these were stacked in an alternating sequence to a total of 14 layers. These types of glass and stacking sequence are similar to that used in some naval vessels [8]. The glass preforms were then stitched through-the-thickness with Kevlar®-49 thread using a modified lock stitch to a low (3 stitches/cm²) or high (6 stitches/cm²) stitch density. The non-stitched and stitched glass preforms were then impregnated with a vinyl ester resin (Derakane® 411) using vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (RTM), and cured under ambient conditions to produce a laminate with a polymer content of about 40% by weight. The RTM produced non-stitched and stitched composite panels with a length of 1 m, width of 0.5 m and thickness of about 6.1 mm. The panels were cut into smaller rectangular specimens (270 mm long x 70 mm wide) for underwater explosion testing. Five types of laminate were tested:

- (1) non-stitched laminate,
- (2) laminate stitched along the length (or longitudinal direction) with a low stitch density,
- (3) laminate stitched along the length (or longitudinal direction) with a high stitch density,
- (4) laminate stitched across the width (or transverse direction) with a low density,
- (5) laminate stitched across the width (or transverse direction) with a high stitch density.

The specimens with the stitch orientation in the transverse direction were cut from the large panels at a 90° angle from the specimens stitched in the longitudinal direction.

The response of the laminates to underwater shock loading was studied in a small-scale explosive shock testing facility. A schematic representation of the shock testing procedure is shown in Fig. 1, and further details of the testing technique and facility are described by Mouritz *et al.* [2] and Mouritz [3-5,7]. A laminate was attached to an air-tight box by rubber-lined clamps, which allowed the specimen to bend relatively freely under the impulse load exerted by the underwater shock wave. The shock wave was generated by an explosive made from plastic explosive type 4 (cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine), which was placed directly above the laminate. The laminates were tested under two shock (impulse force) conditions: (1) *low shock loading*, which was produced by a 15.8 g explosive positioned 1.0 m above the specimen, and (2) *high shock loading*, which was generated by a 50.0 g explosive placed 0.9 m above the specimen. The pressure-time response of the shock wave was measured by an underwater pressure gauge (type PCB 135A05) attached to the front surface of the laminate, and recorded by a Norland Prowler digital waveform analyser. Fig. 2 shows the pressure-time profiles for the shock wave for the (a) low and (b) high shock loading conditions. Both profiles were similar in shape, with the only significant difference being that the peak pressures for the low and high shock conditions were about 13 MPa and 26 MPa, respectively. Three specimens of the non-stitched and stitched laminates were tested for the two shock conditions. After testing the laminates were cut along their length to produce two specimens of equal size (270 mm long by ~34 mm wide), producing a total of six specimens for each shock condition. Five of the specimens were used for measuring the residual in-plane flexural properties while the remaining specimen was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to observe any microstructural damage caused by shock loading. The flexural testing was performed using the four-point bend method according to ASTM D790M-84 [9]. A load and support span of 70 mm and 140 mm, respectively, was used, and the shock-tested laminates were

bend at a strain rate of $\sim 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to failure to determine their residual flexural properties (elastic modulus and maximum flexural strength).

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of the underwater explosion shock loading technique. The underwater shock wave produced by an explosive applied a uniform impulse load over the laminate. The rubber grips allowed the laminate to bend freely under the shock pressure.

Figure 2. Pressure-time profiles of the underwater shock waves measured at the laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the in-plane flexural properties of the non-stitched and stitched laminates before shock testing, and after being tested under the low and high shock loading conditions. These values for (a) maximum flexural strength and (b) elastic modulus are the average of five four-point bend measurements. The values shown in brackets in Table 1a are the standard deviations in the strength measurements, whereas the elastic modulus values had no appreciable scatter. Before shock testing, the flexural properties of the non-stitched laminate were about 10% higher than the stitched laminates. This reveals that stitching degraded the in-plane flexural properties, and similar results have been observed in stitched graphite/epoxy [10] and Kevlar®/epoxy [11] laminates under three-point bending. This reduction was due to damage of the glass fibres and disruption of the fibre architecture which occurred during the stitching operation. It was also due to the stitches being stress concentration sites during bending, promoting microstructural damage at lower flexural strengths than in the non-stitched material [11-13]. Table 1a shows that the flexural strengths of the different stitched laminates were similar, indicating that this property was not affected by the stitch direction or stitch density. However, Table 1b shows that the elastic modulus of the laminates stitched in the transverse direction were slightly higher than in the longitudinal direction for the same stitch density, and the elastic modulus was higher in the laminates with the low stitch density.

Table 1a. The maximum flexural strengths of the stitched and non-stitched laminates before shock testing, and after testing at the low and high shock conditions.

Laminate	Before Shock Testing	Low Shock Condition	High Shock Condition
Non-Stitched	369 (± 15) MPa	337 (± 25) MPa	71 (± 69) MPa
Longitudinal, High Density	324 (± 37) MPa	283 (± 49) MPa	318 (± 24) MPa
Longitudinal, Low Density	327 (± 12) MPa	298 (± 44) MPa	211 (± 105) MPa
Transverse, High Density	334 (± 28) MPa	268 (± 44) MPa	47 (± 4) MPa
Transverse, Low Density	330 (± 15) MPa	316 (± 15) MPa	100 (± 45) MPa

Table 1b. The elastic modulus of the stitched and non-stitched laminates before shock testing, and after testing at the low and high shock conditions.

Laminate	Before Shock Testing	Low Shock Condition	High Shock Condition
Non-Stitched	21 GPa	16 GPa	5 GPa
Longitudinal, High Density	12 GPa	12 GPa	12 GPa
Longitudinal, Low Density	16 GPa	12 GPa	8 GPa
Transverse, High Density	16 GPa	13 GPa	2 GPa
Transverse, Low Density	19 GPa	14 GPa	3 GPa

Table 1 shows a slight reduction (of between 5% and 30%) in the flexural properties after the laminates were tested under the low shock condition. SEM examination revealed no damage to the glass fibres or Kevlar® threads, and only a small amount of cracking of the polymer matrix and small delaminations between the polymer and fibres. This damage is believed to result from the flexural stresses experienced by the laminates as they bend under the impulse load of the shock wave. Further details of the damage mechanisms in other GRP laminates exposed to underwater explosions are described in refs 2-5,7. The small amount of damage to the laminates accounts for the slight reduction in their properties. However, because the residual flexural properties of the stitched laminates remained lower than the non-stitched material, it appears that stitching will not improve the damage resistance of GRP naval vessels when struck by low pressure shock waves.

When tested at the high shock condition, Table 1 shows that the flexural properties of the non-stitched laminate and the transverse stitched laminates were reduced considerably (by 70% to 90%). The appearance of these laminates was changed by the shock loading, as shown in Fig. 3, due to the formation of damage beneath the surface. The damaged region is apparent in the photographs as the discoloured area across the centre. These photographs show the top surface of the specimens without the need for background illumination to high-light the damaged area. The non-stitched laminate (Fig 3a) and laminate stitched in the transverse direction (Fig 3b) both show a relatively wide-spread damaged zone, although the damaged area was slightly smaller in

Figure 3. Photographs of the (a) non-stitched laminate, (b) transverse stitched laminate and (c) longitudinal stitched laminate both with a high stitch density after testing at the high shock condition. The discoloured region near the centre is caused by microstructural damage beneath the surface.

the stitched material. SEM revealed that the microstructures of these laminates contained the same types of damage, including cracking of the polymer (Fig. 4a), wide-spread delaminations (Fig. 4b), compressive buckling and tensile fracture of the glass plies (Fig. 4c) and, in the stitched material, localised failure of the Kevlar® stitches across the widest delaminations (Fig. 4d). This extensive damage accounts for the large reductions in the flexural properties of these laminates. In contrast, Table 1 shows that the laminates stitched in the longitudinal direction retained most of their strength and stiffness, particularly the material with the high stitch density. In these laminates the only sign of damage was thin bands of discolouration across the material, as shown in Fig. 3c. Microstructural examination of these materials revealed that the glass fibres and Kevlar® stitches remained undamaged, although some cracking of the polymer and small delaminations were observed. Most of this damage was localised to the GRP microstructure around the stitch holes, which are expected to be stress concentration sites during the bending loads under shock loading. The cause of the laminates having a higher damage resistance when stitched in the longitudinal direction compared with the transverse direction remains unclear. However, the results suggest that under the dynamic loading conditions generated by an underwater shock wave, where strain rates of $10\text{-}100\text{ s}^{-1}$ are expected, the interlaminar fracture properties are significantly higher when the stitch rows are in the longitudinal direction. Nevertheless, these tests performed under the high shock condition indicate that naval vessels made from GRP stitched in a longitudinal orientation will exhibit a higher resistance to damage when struck by a high pressure shock wave compared with traditional non-stitched laminates.

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrographs of damage within the laminates caused by the high pressure shock wave. (a) Cracking within the polymer matrix. (b) Delamination between the polymer and glass ply. (c) Compressive buckling of a glass ply. (d) Failure of a Kevlar® thread across a delamination.

CONCLUSIONS

From this study of the effect of underwater shock loading on the flexural properties of stitched GRP laminates the following conclusions may be made :

1. The flexural strength and stiffness of the laminates are reduced by about 10% when stitched with Kevlar® thread because of the damage and disturbance of the glass preform during the stitching process, and by the stitches acting as stress concentration sites during bending.
2. When impulsively loaded by a low pressure shock wave which creates minor damage in the GRP microstructure (principally polymer cracking and small delaminations), the laminates experience a slight reduction in their flexural properties. Stitching does not appear to suppress these damage processes, and consequently no improvement to damage resistance appears to be gained by stitching under low pressure loading.
3. Under high shock conditions the laminates stitched in the longitudinal direction show a greater damage resistance and higher residual flexural properties than the non-stitched laminate and the laminates stitched in the transverse direction.

REFERENCES

1. C.S. Smith, *Design of Marine Structures in Composite Materials*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1990.
2. A.P. Mouritz, D.S. Saunders and S. Buckley, The damage and failure of GRP laminates by underwater explosion shock loading, *Comp.* **25**, 431-437 (1994).
3. A.P. Mouritz, The effect of underwater explosion shock loading on the fatigue behaviour of GRP laminates, *Comp.* **26**, 3-9 (1995).
4. A.P. Mouritz, The effect of processing on the underwater explosion shock behaviour of GRP laminates, *J. Comp. Mat.* (In press).
5. A.P. Mouritz, The effect of underwater explosion shock loading on the flexural properties of GRP laminates, *Int. J. Impact Engng.* (Submitted for publication).
6. K. Dransfield, C. Baillie and Y.W. Mai, Improving the delamination resistance of CFRP by stitching - a review, *Comp. Sci. Tech.* **50**, 305-317 (1994).
7. A.P. Mouritz, The damage to stitched GRP laminates by underwater explosion shock loading, *Comp. Sci. Tech.* (Submitted for publication).
8. D.J. Hall, Examination of the effects of underwater blasts on sandwich composite structures, *Comp. Struct.* **11**, 101-120 (1989).
9. ASTM D790M-84, Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials (metric), *ASTM Standards and Literature References for Composite Materials*, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia (1984).
10. H. Harris, N. Schinske, N. Krueger and B. Swanson, Multiaxial stitched preform reinforcements for RTM fabrication, *36th Int. SAMPE Symp.*, pp. 521-535 (April 15-18, 1991).
11. M.T. Cholakara, B.Z. Jang and C.Z. Wang, Deformation and failure mechanisms in 3D composites, *34th Int. SAMPE Conf.*, pp. 2153-2160 (May 8-11, 1989).
12. A.P. Mouritz, Flexural properties of stitched GRP laminates, *Composites*. (Submitted for publication).
13. T.J. Kang and S.H. Lee, Effect of stitching on the mechanical and impact properties of woven laminate composite, *J. Comp. Mat.* **28**, 1574-1587 (1994).

